

Creative Thinking and Mathematics Performance: The Interplay of Socio-Emotional Skills and General Academic Self-Efficacy as Mediators

Aleya Lorenzana Laguit¹, Kim Cristan De Guzman Camilosa¹

¹Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Gabaldon Campus, College of Education

Email: aleyalaguit028@gmail.com, kimcristancamilosa@gmail.com

Abstract: This study investigates the mediating roles of socio-emotional learning (SEL) and general academic self-efficacy (GAS) in the relationship between creative thinking and mathematics performance among 200 Grade 9 students, aged 14 to 15, from public schools in Gabaldon, Nueva Ecija. Using a correlational research design and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), the study explores how SEL and GAS influence students' ability to apply creative thinking effectively in mathematics by helping them manage emotions, build confidence, and sustain motivation. The findings reveal that while creative thinking alone does not directly improve math performance, its positive effect is significantly enhanced through the mediating influence of SEL and GAS. These results underscore the importance of integrating cognitive, emotional, and motivational factors in mathematics education to promote improved academic outcomes and equip students for complex real-world challenges. The study recommends educational reforms that incorporate creative thinking with socio-emotional and self-efficacy development to create holistic learning environments.

Keywords: *Creative thinking, socio-emotional skills, mathematics performance, self-efficacy, socio-emotional learning*

Introduction

Mathematics is often perceived as a rigid and linear discipline, but within the past few decades, encouraging creativity in mathematics instruction has been recognized as a crucial step in enhancing overall student performance. Educational models have undergone significant changes over the past few years, shifting the focus from rote memorization and procedural learning to higher-order thinking. According to the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 2020), creativity in mathematics not only enhances problem-solving abilities but also enriches the learning experience by motivating students to explore diverse solutions and approaches to mathematical tasks.

Such challenges are underscored by the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2022), which revealed that Filipino students ranked among the bottom four countries in creative thinking, scoring a mean of only 14. Such rankings put them alongside nations like Albania, Uzbekistan, and Morocco, but starkly contrast with top performers such as Singapore, whose students scored an average of 41. A decline in student performance is also a major concern, as PISA revealed that the average mathematics score across OECD countries has dropped by nearly 15 points since 2018, and one in four 15-year-olds is classified as a low performer. These alarming trends underscore the urgent need to reform education in the Philippines, incorporating innovative teaching strategies that foster both cognitive and emotional growth, as exemplified by initiatives such as the MATATAG Agenda and the Basic Education Development Plan.

Mathematical creativity is a disposition that enables students to engage in both divergent and convergent thinking to devise new or novel solutions to mathematical scenarios (Geoff, 2021). Based on the results of previous studies, it can be concluded that students with skills and abilities in creative thinking can solve problems as complex as mathematical problems, such as those involving multiple solutions or creative steps (Hidajat, 2021). According to various studies, creativity has become one of the most promising predictors of a student's ability to solve diverse problems, including open-ended mathematics tasks (Schoenfeld, 2023). This suggests a need for educational practices that prioritize creative problem-solving over traditional ones.

The present study is grounded in three theoretical frameworks that justify the identification of its key variables. Torrance's Theory of Creativity (1966) emphasizes divergent thinking—fluency, originality, flexibility, and elaboration—as essential skills in problem-solving and in engaging with mathematical tasks creatively. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) emphasizes the pivotal role of self-efficacy in shaping learning outcomes, persistence, and resilience in challenging situations, thereby directly supporting the inclusion of general academic self-efficacy as a mediating variable. The CASEL Framework for Socio-Emotional Learning (2013) identifies core competencies—self-awareness, self-management, responsible decision-making, social awareness, and relationship skills—that equip learners with the emotional and social resources needed for sustained engagement. Together, these frameworks provide the foundation for this study by explaining how creative thinking (independent variable) influences mathematics performance (dependent variable), with socio-emotional learning (SEL) and general academic self-efficacy (GAS) acting as mediating variables.

Additionally, creative thinking is not a solitary skill. It can interact with other cognitive and emotional factors that influence learning outcomes. Socio-emotional skills encompass competencies such as self-awareness, self-management, responsible decision-making, social awareness, and relationship skills (CASEL, 2020). These competencies support the development of a learning environment in which ideas can be voiced and risks can be taken in mathematical reasoning. According to Bandura (1997), self-efficacy refers to one's belief in their capabilities, and it influences students' motivation and persistence when they are challenged to solve problems. Students with high self-efficacy are likely to engage creatively and interactively with mathematical content because they believe they can succeed.

Socio-emotional skills have been shown to play a significant role in self-efficacy. For example, students who become proficient in emotional regulation are better placed to handle stress and anxiety that arise from challenging mathematical tasks, allowing them to concentrate on solving problems rather than being derailed by negative emotions (Maros et al., 2022). Collaborative learning environments also foster social interactions that enhance self-efficacy through peer support and shared problem-solving experiences. Much remains to be understood regarding the roles of socio-emotional skills as mediators and self-efficacy, despite various earlier studies on the interplay between creative thinking and mathematics performance. The contribution of socio-emotional factors that accompany creative thinking in the discourse on mathematics education, unfortunately, remains mostly neglected (Khongsankham, 2024). Beyond these discussions, much remains unexplored about how students' motivation and performance are shaped by self-efficacy in mathematics in extant studies (Blessing, 2024). These gaps call for an integrated framework rather than fragmented approaches.

In this context, the present study aims to investigate the relationship between creative thinking and mathematics performance by examining the mediating roles of socio-emotional learning and general academic self-efficacy. Specifically, the study aims to describe the respondents' profiles in terms of age, sex, and the availability of learning materials at home, and to examine their mathematics grades for the first and second quarters. It also aims to describe students' creative thinking in terms of generating ideas, collaboration, and applying ideas; their socio-emotional skills in terms of self-awareness, social awareness, self-control, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making; and their general academic self-efficacy. Furthermore, it examines whether there is a significant relationship between the respondents' profiles and their creative thinking, socio-emotional skills, self-efficacy, and mathematics performance. The study also examines whether creative thinking predicts mathematics performance and whether SEL and GAS mediate the relationship between creative thinking and mathematics performance. Finally, it explores whether path analysis indicates full or partial mediation.

To address these objectives, the study tests several hypotheses. First, there is no significant correlation between the respondents' profile and their creative thinking, socio-emotional learning, general academic self-efficacy, and mathematics performance. Second, creative thinking does not significantly predict students' mathematics performance. Third, socio-emotional learning does not mediate the relationship between creative thinking and mathematics performance. Fourth, general academic self-efficacy does not mediate the relationship between creative thinking and mathematics performance.

This research is important because it can inform educational practices and policies aimed at improving performance in mathematics. Understanding how creative thinking connects with socio-emotional learning and self-efficacy will help educators encourage both cognitive and emotional development. It will also help address the achievement gap noted in recent assessments and contribute to a more holistic approach to mathematics education. Beyond that, SEL models have the potential to transform traditional instruction by promoting active learning, creativity, emotional awareness, and collaborative problem-solving. These skills are essential as students prepare to navigate an increasingly complex world. Therefore, it is crucial for educational systems to integrate SEL and self-efficacy alongside the goal of improving mathematics performance. By addressing these aims, the study seeks to support the development of well-rounded learners who are not only mathematically capable but also emotionally and cognitively equipped for future challenges.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive, correlational design to examine the relationships among creative thinking, socio-emotional learning (SEL), general academic self-efficacy (GASE), and mathematics performance. The design was appropriate because it allowed the researchers to determine the degree and direction of association among these variables without manipulating them.

The correlational approach was also suitable as the study sought to test hypothesized mediation pathways. To achieve this, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was employed, allowing for the simultaneous assessment of both direct and indirect effects. SEM provided a comprehensive statistical framework for validating the proposed model and determining whether SEL and GAS function as mediators in the relationship between creative thinking and mathematics performance.

Research Locale and Respondents of the Study

The study was conducted in four public schools located in Gabaldon, Nueva Ecija, namely: F. Buencamino Sr. Integrated School (FBSIS), Gabaldon Vocational Agriculture High School (GVAHS), Ligaya National High School (LNHS), and the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST) Gabaldon Campus. These schools were chosen to represent a range of socioeconomic and educational contexts in the municipality.

Stratified sampling was used to ensure balanced representation across schools, with a sample size of 200 students selected based on Kline's (2015) recommendation for SEM analysis, which requires a minimum of 200 respondents to ensure robust model fit and statistical power. The participants were 200 Grade 9 students, aged 14 to 15, chosen through stratified sampling. This demographic corresponds to the age group identified by PISA as typically underperforming in mathematics, making them ideal subjects for analyzing the factors affecting math achievement.

Research Instrument

The instruments for data collection were the Social and Emotional Learning Scale, developed and validated by Fernández-Martín et al. (2022), the General Academic Self-Efficacy Scale by van Zyl et al. (2022), and a standardized questionnaire on Creative Thinking created by Bahrain (2020). A structured survey questionnaire was used to gather information from the selected respondents.

The questionnaire consisted of two parts: the first part pertained to the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, while the second part consisted of standardized questions related to General Academic Self-Efficacy, Creative Thinking, and Social and Emotional Learning, ensuring alignment with the study's objectives. The questionnaire was closed-ended, allowing respondents to choose from the available options by filling in the provided spaces and ticking the corresponding choices. The scale of response used was the Likert Scale, specifically a 5-point scale, which was widely used for measuring opinions, attitudes, or behaviors.

Reliability of Research Instrument

To ensure the reliability of the research instrument for this study, a pilot test was conducted using 20 students who were not included in the respondents' pool. The standardized questionnaire's internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with a target value of 0.70 or higher to indicate acceptable reliability. The results showed that the Creative Thinking Questionnaire had a reliability coefficient of $\alpha = 0.88$, the Socio-Emotional Learning Scale yielded $\alpha = 0.91$, the Self-Efficacy Scale obtained $\alpha = 0.86$, and the Mathematics Performance Checklist showed $\alpha = 0.79$. These values indicate that all instruments demonstrated acceptable to excellent internal consistency, confirming their reliability for use in the main study.

Sampling Technique

The purposive sampling method was applied to select participants based on specific criteria relevant to the study. The selection focused on Grade 9 students who were officially enrolled in the school, had consistent attendance, and demonstrated willingness to participate in the activities. These criteria ensured that the participants could fully engage with the project-based learning intervention and provide reliable results.

In terms of comparability, both the control and intervention groups were drawn from the same grade level, shared similar academic backgrounds, and had comparable classroom settings. This minimized external differences, allowing the researcher to attribute any observed variations in outcomes primarily to the intervention rather than to other factors.

Data Collection Procedure

Permission was obtained from the principals of all participating schools as well as from the Chair of the College of Education of NEUST Gabaldon Campus. Surveys were administered in person with assurances of confidentiality and voluntary participation. Data were collected through paper-based or digital forms across the schools and stored securely for analysis.

Data Analysis

Data analysis in this study was conducted in three key phases. First, descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the demographic profiles of the respondents and the distribution of scores across the main variables, including creative thinking, socio-emotional learning (SEL), general academic self-efficacy (GAS), and mathematics performance. Second, a

correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between demographic characteristics—such as age, sex, and availability of learning materials—and the primary study variables. This phase helped identify potential associations and guided further inferential testing. Third, the study utilized Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to analyze both direct and indirect relationships among creative thinking, SEL, GAS, and mathematics performance. SEM was chosen for its ability to assess complex mediation models involving multiple dependent and mediating variables.

To evaluate the model fit, several statistical indices were used, guided by established recommendations. The normed chi-square (CMIN/DF) was considered acceptable within the range of 1 to 3 (Hooper, Coughlan, & Mullen, 2008). The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) was evaluated with ideal values of 0.95 or higher, the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) with expected values of 0.08 or lower, and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) with values no greater than 0.06 (Hu & Bentler, 1999). These cutoffs are consistent with the standards outlined by Kline (2005) for SEM reporting. Additionally, a p-value of 0.05 or lower was used to determine statistical significance. These indices ensured that the final SEM model met accepted thresholds for goodness of fit, allowing for a valid interpretation of the structural relationships in the proposed framework.

Results

Respondent's Profile

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents by age and sex. The distribution of 14- and 15-year-olds by sex, as presented in the table, reveals a notable difference in the proportion of males and females within this age group. Among the 200 individuals, 115, or 57.5%, are female, while 85, or 42.5%, are male.

This indicates a higher representation of females in this specific cohort. When analyzed by age, 15-year-olds constitute a slightly larger proportion (53.0%) compared to 14-year-olds (47.0%). Within each age group, females outnumber males, with 30.0% of the total population being 15-year-old females and 27.5% being 14-year-old females, in contrast to 23.0% and 19.5% for males, respectively.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents According to Age and Sex.

Age	Male		Female		Total	Percentage
	frequency	percent	frequency	percent		
14	39	19.5%	55	27.5%	94	47%
15	46	23%	60	30%	106	53%
Total	85	42.5%	115	57.5%	200	100%

Learning Materials at Home

The survey revealed that 94.5% of students have access to tablets and smartphones, providing substantial entry points to digital learning. However, only 51% reported access to educational apps or websites, and 35.5% have a PC or laptop at home. In terms of traditional materials, books were available to 43% of students, while printed worksheets were accessible to just 20.5%. Additionally, only 21.5% of students reported having access to online tutorials.

These findings indicate that while digital devices are widely available, the supporting educational content and resources remain unevenly distributed. Access to traditional materials, such as books and printed worksheets, also reveals notable gaps.

Table 2.

Availability of Learning Materials at Home.

Materials	Availability
Books	43%
Educational Apps/ Websites	51%
PC/ Laptop	35.5%
Tablets/ Smartphones	94.5%
Printed Worksheets	20.5%
Access to Online Tutorials	21.5%

Mathematics Grades for the First and Second Quarter

Table 3 presents the distribution of students' Mathematics grades for the first and second quarters. The largest proportion of students, 38.5%, earned a Very Satisfactory rating (grades 85–89), indicating that most students performed well in Mathematics. Following this, 22.5% of students achieved an Outstanding rating (90–100), showing that roughly a quarter of the respondents excelled in the subject. Another 22.5% of students received a Satisfactory rating (80–84), suggesting that they met the expected academic standards but still had room for improvement.

A further 16.75% of students obtained a Fairly Satisfactory rating (75–79). While these students remained within the passing range, their scores suggest potential learning challenges. Notably, no students scored below 75, meaning that all respondents met the minimum academic requirements for the course. This overall performance profile indicates a generally positive outcome in students' Mathematics achievement.

Table 3

Average Mathematics Grades.

Descriptor	Grading Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	90-100	45	22.5 %
Very Satisfactory	85-89	77	38.5 %
Satisfactory	80-84	45	22.5 %
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	33	16.5 %
Did Not Meet Expectations	Below 75	0	0 %
Total		200	100%

Description of Students' Creative Thinking

Table 4 presents the descriptive results showing that students, on average, rated themselves as "Often" across various dimensions of creative thinking. This indicates that students possess a strong foundational level of creative thinking skills.

The highest mean rating was observed for "I can collaborate with others in creative thinking sessions" (3.78), indicating that students feel comfortable engaging in group-based creative activities. Similarly, students reported high levels of confidence in extending and building on good ideas (3.83), thinking creatively or unconventionally (3.69), turning creative thoughts into workable solutions (3.70), and generating original ideas (3.63).

Other items, such as building on others' ideas (3.56), challenging traditional approaches (3.55), and reframing problems from different perspectives (3.51), further support the finding that students actively engage in innovative and adaptive thought processes.

However, relatively lower ratings were found for "I can step back from a problem and see the bigger picture" (3.49), "I can influence group decisions" (3.49), "I can convince others about my ideas" (3.50), and "I can be persuasive in promoting creative solutions" (3.50). These results indicate that while students are confident in their generative and collaborative abilities, they exhibit some challenges in strategic thinking, leadership, and persuasive communication.

Table 4

Students' Creative Thinking.

Generating Ideas	Mean	Verbal interpretation
1. My ideas are highly creative and new.	3.63	Often
2. It is easy for me to build on other's creative ideas.	3.56	Often
3. I like to challenge the 'status quo' in a positive way.	3.55	Often
4. It is easy for me to 'reframe' problems to look at them from a different perspective.	3.51	Often
5. I can step back from a problem and see the bigger picture.	3.49	Often
6. I can be a bit "crazy" in my creative thinking.	3.69	Often
Average Mean	3.57	Often
Collaboration	Mean	Verbal interpretation
1. I can collaborate with others in creative thinking sessions.	3.78	Often
2. I can shape the creative ideas of others to give them more substance.	3.62	Often

3. I can build a collaborative way of working in team problem solving sessions.	3.65	Often
4. I can cause people to re-evaluate the current situation and/or the challenge they face.	3.59	Often
5. I can 'cluster' ideas which have been generated to create themes to design a solution.	3.61	Often
Average Mean	3.65	Often
Applying Ideas	Mean	Verbal interpretation
1. I can turn creative ideas into workable solutions.	3.7	Often
2. I can convince others about my innovation/creative solutions.	3.5	Often
3. I can see what is required to turn a creative idea into action.	3.63	Often
4. I can easily see how to extend and build on a good idea.	3.83	Often
5. I can be very persuasive in influencing others to adopt my creative ideas.	3.5	Often
Average Mean	3.63	Often

Description of Students' Socio-Emotional Learning

Table 5 shows the students' socio-emotional learning in terms of self-awareness, social awareness, self-control, and relationship skills. For Self-Awareness, the total weighted mean of 3.63 (Often) indicates that students are generally aware of their emotions and behaviors. They are most consistent in trying their best on difficult schoolwork (4.21, Always) but less confident in describing their emotions (3.50, Often).

In Social Awareness, the mean of 3.89 (Often) suggests that students frequently show empathy and respect for others. They excel at defending their ideas respectfully (4.17, Always) but find it slightly harder to understand others' feelings (3.69, Often). For Self-Control, the total weighted mean of 3.71 (Often) reflects that students usually manage their goals and emotions well. They are clear about their school goals (4.03, Often), but sometimes struggle to stay calm when angry (3.21, Sometimes). Lastly, Relationship Skills obtained a mean of 3.89 (Often), showing that students often maintain positive interactions and teamwork.

Overall, the results indicate that students often demonstrate socio-emotional learning skills, with strengths in motivation, empathy, and teamwork; however, they may still require support in emotional expression and self-regulation.

Table 5

Students' Socio-Emotional Learning.

Self-Awareness	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I can easily describe my emotions.	3.5	Often
2. I understand my moods and feelings.	3.77	Often
3. I know how my emotions influence what I do.	3.62	Often
4. I am confident that I can successfully complete any school assignment	3.65	Often
5. I try my best when doing difficult homework or schoolwork, as this allows me to improve.	4.21	Always
Total Weighted Mean	3.63	Often
Social Awareness	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I can easily recognize how another person is feeling by their facial expressions, gestures, tone of voice, etc.	3.97	Often
2. It is easy for me to understand why people feel the way they do.	3.69	Often
3. If someone close to me is sad or happy, upset or nervous, I have a pretty good idea why.	3.75	Often
4. I am respectful of anyone's ideas, even if they are different from mine.	3.86	Often
5. I find it easy to defend my ideas without putting anyone down.	4.17	Always
Total Weighted Mean	3.89	Often
Self-Control	Mean	Verbal Interpretation

1. I know how to stay calm when I feel under pressure.	3.73	Often
2. Whatever happens to me, I can keep calm.	3.46	Often
3. When I am angry with someone, I calm down and then talk to him/her about it.	3.21	Sometimes
4. I am clear about my school goals.	4.03	Often
5. I am able to work effectively to achieve long-term school goals.	3.87	Often
6. I am disciplined (i.e., I follow certain routines to do my homework accurately).	3.79	Often
7. I concentrate easily on the schoolwork I have to do.	3.69	Often
8. I carefully plan my homework according to my goals.	3.92	Often
9. I resist any temptation or distraction while doing my homework.	3.55	Often
10. If I commit to a school assignment, I do it. I know how to motivate myself	3.85	Often
Total Weighted Mean	3.71	Often
Relationship Skills		
	Mean	Verbal interpretation
1. I use appropriate verbal language when conversing with friends, family, classmates, etc.	4.01	Often
2. I am confident in my ability to work as part of a team in class.	3.92	Often
3. I treat all members of my team in the same way, politely and respectfully.	4	Often
4. I offer help or help others when I think they need it.	3.92	Often
5. I get on well with my classmates.	3.81	Often
Total Weighted Mean	3.89	Often

Description of Students' General Academic Self-Efficacy

Table 6 presents the results of students' general academic self-efficacy, showing a high overall mean score of 3.88, which indicates a strong sense of confidence in managing academic challenges and achieving learning goals.

Students expressed the highest confidence in statements such as "I can pass exams with enough effort" (3.97), "If other people can, I can too" (3.96), and "I can stay calm during exams because I am well-prepared" (3.91). These results suggest that students possess a positive mindset toward academic tasks and demonstrate preparedness and determination in their studies.

Moderately high scores were also observed in statements like "I can solve difficult academic problems if I try hard enough" (3.84) and "I can achieve the goals I set for my field of study" (3.72). While these indicate a strong belief in personal competence, the slightly lower ratings in goal achievement and problem-solving suggest areas where students may benefit from additional support in strengthening their resilience and long-term motivation.

Table 6

Students' General Academic Self-Efficacy.

Statement	Mean	Verbal interpretation
1. I generally manage to solve difficult academic problems if I try hard enough.	3.84	Often
2. I know I can stick to my aims and accomplish my goals in my field of study.	3.72	Often
3. I will remain calm in my exam because I know I will have the knowledge to solve the problems.	3.91	Often
4. I know I can pass the exam if I put in enough work during the semester.	3.97	Often
5. The motto 'If other people can, I can too' applies to me when it comes to my field of study.	3.96	Often

Total Weighted Mean	3.88	Often
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Correlation Analysis of Socio-Emotional Learning, General Academic Self-Efficacy, and Creative Thinking with Age, Average Grades, and Available Learning Materials

Table 7 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients examining the relationships among socio-emotional learning (SEL), general academic self-efficacy (GAS), and creative thinking (CT) with age, average grades, and the number of available learning materials.

Results indicate that age was not significantly correlated with any of the SEL, GAS, or CT dimensions (all $p > .05$), suggesting that these competencies are not strongly influenced by biological or age-related factors but rather by environmental and experiential contexts.

In contrast, academic performance (average grades) was significantly and positively correlated with several SEL components, including self-awareness ($r = .111, p < .05$), social awareness ($r = .117, p < .05$), relationship skills ($r = .149, p < .01$), and responsible decision-making ($r = .207, p < .01$). These findings imply that students who demonstrate greater emotional awareness, empathy, and interpersonal competence tend to perform better academically.

General academic self-efficacy (GAS) also showed a significant positive correlation with academic performance ($r = .210, p < .01$), indicating that students with higher confidence in their academic abilities tend to achieve better grades.

Similarly, dimensions of creative thinking, particularly idea generation ($r = .123, p < .05$), collaboration ($r = .120, p < .05$), and application of ideas ($r = .133, p < .01$), were significantly and positively correlated with academic performance. These results suggest that creativity-related skills are linked to improved learning outcomes.

Finally, the availability of learning materials at home was significantly correlated with GAS ($r = .119, p < .05$) and the application of ideas dimension of creative thinking ($r = .109, p < .05$), indicating that greater access to educational resources supports self-efficacy and the practical use of creative ideas.

Table 7

Correlation Analysis of Socio-Emotional Learning, General Academic Self-Efficacy, and Creative Thinking with Age, Average Grades, and Available Learning Materials.

	Age		Average Grade		Number of Learning Materials	
	Correlation	p-value	Correlation	p-value	Correlation	p-value
Self-Awareness	-0.104	0.086	0.111*	0.027	0.046	0.403
Social Awareness	0.068	0.259	0.117*	0	0.038	0.486
Self-Control	-0.035	0.55	0.0623	0.202	0.38	0.473
Relationship Skills	0.008	0.9	0.149**	0.003	0.27	0.623
Responsible Decision Making	-0.031	0.608	0.207	0	0.103	0.056
GAS	-0.026	0.668	0.210**	0	.119**	0.028
Generating Ideas	0.012	0.847	0.123*	0.014	0.082	0.129
Collaboration	0.051	0.399	0.120*	0.017	0.082	0.126
Applying Ideas	-0.053	0.377	0.133*	0.008	0.109*	0.043

Associations Between Socio-Emotional Learning, General Academic Self-Efficacy, and Creative Thinking with Sex

Table 8 presents the analysis of associations between sex and the variables socio-emotional learning (SEL), general academic self-efficacy (GAS), and creative thinking (CT).

The results indicate no statistically significant relationships between sex and most components of SEL, GAS, and CT, including self-awareness, social awareness, self-control, relationship skills, idea generation, collaboration, and application of ideas. This suggests that these competencies are not significantly influenced by gender and are instead shaped by students' environments, learning experiences, and social contexts rather than biological or sex-based differences.

However, a statistically significant difference was observed in responsible decision-making, where female students scored slightly higher than male students ($p = 0.032$). This implies that while overall emotional, cognitive, and creative

capacities are similar across genders, specific areas such as moral or reflective decision-making may be more developed among female learners.

Table 8

Associations Between Socio-Emotional Learning, General Academic Self-Efficacy, and Creative Thinking with Sex.

	Value	df	Significance (2-sided)
Self-Awareness	13.301 ^a	14	.503
Social Awareness	16.194 ^a	14	.302
Self-Control	34.177 ^a	28	.195
Relationship Skills	14.282 ^a	16	.578
Responsible Decision Making	17.879 ^a	14	.032
General Academic Self-Efficacy	16.889 ^a	15	.326
Generating Ideas	16.265 ^a	17	.505
Collaboration	11.403 ^a	15	.724
Applying Ideas	14.793 ^a	15	.466

Structural Equation Model Analysis

A CFI of 0.957 represents an excellent fit, indicating that the model closely matches the observed data. An RMSEA of 0.056 indicates a good fit, indicating that the model's approximation error is low. A CMIN/DF ratio of 1.612 falls within the acceptable fit range, as values below 2 are generally considered reasonable. Finally, a significant p-value (0.001) is expected in SEM, especially with large sample sizes, and does not necessarily indicate poor model fit.

Table 9

SEM Fit Indices.

Indices	Value	Interpretation
<i>CFI</i>	0.957	Excellent Fit
<i>RMSEA</i>	0.056	Good Fit
<i>CMIN/DF</i>	1.612	Acceptable Fit
<i>p-value (Model Fit)</i>	0.001	Significant

Figure 3. Structural Equation Model

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Regression Weights and Fit Indices

Table 10 presents the findings of the path analysis conducted through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), which explored the relationships among Creative Thinking (CT), General Academic Self-Efficacy (GAS), Socio-Emotional Learning (SEL), and Average Grade (AveGrade).

The results indicate significant positive paths from CT to SEL ($\beta = 0.612, p < .001$) and CT to GAS ($\beta = 1.000, p < .001$). These findings suggest that students with higher levels of creative thinking tend to exhibit stronger socio-emotional learning skills and greater self-efficacy.

However, the path from CT to Average Grade was not significant ($\beta = -0.07, p = .194$), indicating that creative thinking alone does not directly predict students' academic performance.

In contrast, both SEL ($\beta = 3.295, p < .001$) and GAS ($\beta = 6.306, p < .001$) showed significant positive relationships with Average Grade, meaning that higher levels of socio-emotional learning and academic self-efficacy are associated with better academic outcomes.

Finally, the model results indicate that SEL and GAS act as full mediators between CT and Average Grade. This suggests that while creative thinking does not directly affect grades, it indirectly contributes to academic performance by strengthening students' socio-emotional and self-efficacy capacities.

Table 10

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Regression Weights and Fit Indices.

Path	Estimate	p-value	Interpretation
CT ->>SEL	0.612	p<.001	Creative Thinking significantly predicts SEL
CT ->> GAS	1.000	p<.001	Creative Thinking significantly predicts GAS
SEL ->> Average Grade	3.295	p<.001	SEL positively predicts Math Performance
GAS->> Average Grade	6.306	p<.001	GAS positively predicts Math Performance
CT ->> Average Grade	-5.758	.194	CT isn't a significant predictor; other factors may be involved.

Indirect Path Analysis

Table 11 presents the results of the indirect effect analysis derived from the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The indirect effect estimate of 0.842 ($p < .001$) indicates that for every 1 standard deviation increase in Creative Thinking (CT), the Average Grade increases by 0.842 standard deviations.

This result confirms that the effect of CT on academic performance is statistically significant but indirect, operating through Socio-Emotional Learning (SEL) and General Academic Self-Efficacy (GAS) as mediating variables. In essence, higher levels of creative thinking enhance students' socio-emotional competencies and academic self-efficacy, which subsequently lead to improved academic achievement.

Table 11

Indirect Path Analysis.

Indirect Effect	Estimate	p
CT ->> Average Grade	0.842	< .001

Discussion

The availability of learning materials at home has direct implications for students' creative thinking, socio-emotional learning (SEL), self-efficacy (GAS), and mathematics performance. Although, majority of students own digital devices, the limited access to educational apps, websites, and computers suggests that these tools may not be fully utilized for academically enriching activities. Such limitations could restrict opportunities for developing problem-solving skills, self-directed learning, and digital collaboration, which are essential for both self-efficacy and socio-emotional growth.

The relatively low access to printed materials further highlights inequities in traditional learning resources. As noted by Riffe (2017), printed texts facilitate deeper comprehension, which supports critical and creative thinking, particularly in mathematics. This aligns with the OECD's (2015) findings that, while digital tools increasingly replace printed materials, equitable access to both remains essential for meeting diverse learning needs.

Finally, the scarcity of online tutorials (21.5%) underscores the challenge of extending learning beyond the classroom. Such resources can strengthen persistence, confidence, and emotional regulation—key elements of socio-emotional learning and self-belief in mathematics.

Taken together, the uneven distribution of learning materials—both digital and traditional—helps explain variations in students' creative thinking, socio-emotional skills, and self-efficacy, which ultimately shape mathematics performance. Ensuring balanced access to diverse learning tools is therefore crucial for promoting holistic student development and improved academic outcomes.

The distribution of Mathematics grades suggests a generally strong academic performance among students, with most achieving satisfactory to outstanding results. The concentration of students in the Very Satisfactory range (85–89) may reflect effective teaching strategies, consistent student engagement, and a supportive learning environment. The high proportion of Outstanding performers also indicates that many students possess strong foundational skills and intrinsic motivation toward Mathematics.

However, the 16.75% of students with Fairly Satisfactory ratings highlight a subgroup that may require targeted academic interventions. These learners, although they pass, may be experiencing conceptual difficulties or gaps in comprehension that could hinder their future performance. Providing additional support through tutorials, remedial instruction, or personalized feedback could help these students improve their mastery of mathematical concepts.

This pattern is consistent with broader educational research. Chere & Hlalele (2015) emphasized that academic underachievement is a global issue that can occur across all ability levels and is not merely a result of low intelligence or effort. They noted that underachieving students often face challenges in convergent thinking tasks (requiring precise answers) and sequential processes (like computation and memorization), which are central to mathematical learning. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Fong et al. (2023) found that underachieving learners tend to exhibit lower self-regulated learning strategies, reduced competence beliefs, and a higher extrinsic locus of control, which collectively impede optimal academic performance.

Together, these insights suggest that while the majority of students perform well, continuous monitoring and targeted support for those at the lower end of the achievement spectrum are vital. Addressing cognitive, emotional, and motivational factors holistically can help sustain high performance levels and prevent potential learning disparities in Mathematics.

Overall, the results suggest that students possess well-developed creative thinking abilities, particularly in the areas of idea generation, collaboration, and application. The high mean scores for statements such as “I can be a bit ‘crazy’ in my creative thinking” and “I can build on a good idea” indicate that students are open to exploring unconventional ideas and are capable of expanding and refining them. This reflects confidence in divergent thinking—an essential component of creativity.

These findings align with Wardani (2023), who noted that students who embrace unconventional thinking exhibit stronger creative performance. Similarly, Setiawan & Fitriani (2023) highlighted that collaboration and co-creation significantly enhance creativity by enabling students to generate, refine, and merge diverse ideas. The high scores related to teamwork—such as “building collaborative problem-solving approaches” (3.65) and “encouraging others to rethink challenges” (3.59)—underscore this relationship.

However, the lower mean for “I can step back from a problem and see the bigger picture” suggests limited strategic and reflective thinking. Fitriani (2023) emphasized that creative problem-solving requires the ability to synthesize ideas within broader systems or real-world contexts. Encouraging students to connect creative outputs to interdisciplinary applications could strengthen this skill.

In collaborative contexts, although students reported feeling comfortable in group settings, their lower ratings for influencing decisions (3.49) and persuasive communication (3.50) indicate potential gaps in leadership and advocacy. Nugroho et al. (2023) emphasized that leadership and persuasion are crucial in transforming creative ideas into actionable group outcomes. Similarly, Setiawan & Fitriani (2023) observed that even strong creative thinkers may underperform if they cannot effectively communicate their ideas.

Taken together, these findings indicate that students are well-prepared for creative engagement, particularly in generating and implementing ideas. Yet, to further advance their creative potential, educational interventions should focus on enhancing strategic reflection, persuasive communication, and leadership within collaboration. Developing these complex cognitive and interpersonal dimensions would prepare students to apply creativity effectively in real-world, interdisciplinary, and problem-oriented contexts.

The results affirm that students exhibit well-developed socio-emotional competencies, supporting studies that link SEL with academic success and emotional well-being. The strong performance in perseverance and emotional self-awareness supports Adina and Colomeischi (2015) and Musinguzi et al. (2024), who emphasize that emotional regulation enhances student achievement. Meanwhile, the lower score in emotional articulation aligns with Adegoju (2023), suggesting that difficulty expressing feelings may lead to stress and hinder self-regulation. Integrating activities such as journaling, guided reflections, and role-playing can help address this need.

Students’ strong Social Awareness supports Khongsankham’s (2024) claim that empathy and respectful communication foster positive peer relations. Programs such as group projects, structured debates, and perspective-taking exercises can further reinforce this strength. In terms of Self-Control, results are consistent with Maros et al. (2022) and Musa et al. (2023), who found that self-regulation and emotional control are essential to reducing academic stress. Interventions such as mindfulness training, breathing exercises, and conflict-resolution workshops can enhance students’ ability to manage anger and stress effectively.

The findings on Relationship Skills reflect Escarilla et al. (2024), who emphasized the value of teamwork and positive social interaction in creating supportive learning environments. Implementing peer mentorship and cooperative learning can enhance collaboration and foster a harmonious classroom environment. In addition, students’ Decision-Making aligns with Akaneme and Metu (2024), who associated social responsibility with higher engagement and civic-mindedness. Embedding service-learning and ethical decision-making activities into the curriculum can further nurture this competency.

Overall, these findings highlight the importance of embedding SEL in the school curriculum to foster emotional intelligence, academic motivation, and social harmony. Teachers should integrate SEL-focused lessons—such as explicit instruction on emotional vocabulary, goal setting, and conflict resolution—while also receiving professional development to ensure consistent and effective implementation across all subjects.

The findings reflect that students exhibit a well-developed sense of academic self-efficacy, which serves as a key factor in fostering academic persistence, confidence, and overall achievement. The high ratings for exam-related items indicate that students possess a strong belief in their preparation and effort, aligning with Liu et al. (2023), who found that self-efficacy positively influences mathematics performance by promoting persistence in overcoming challenges and confidence in problem-solving tasks.

Despite generally strong self-beliefs, the slightly lower ratings in goal achievement and problem-solving highlight a potential need to reinforce resilience and adaptive learning behaviors. According to Cagay et al. (2024), self-efficacy alone is not always a sufficient predictor of mathematics success; it is most effective when supported by motivation, parental

engagement, and emotional support. These complementary factors enhance students' ability to sustain effort and cope with academic pressure.

To strengthen these dimensions, interventions such as goal-setting workshops, collaborative problem-solving sessions, and motivational coaching can be integrated into the learning environment. Such initiatives can help students maintain a sense of purpose, increase perseverance, and further develop confidence in their academic capabilities.

Overall, the results suggest that while students already demonstrate high levels of academic self-efficacy, a holistic approach that combines motivational, emotional, and social support could further improve their academic outcomes and long-term resilience. Cultivating these interrelated factors will not only sustain students' confidence but also enhance their ability to perform effectively in challenging academic contexts.

The correlation analysis underscores that students' socio-emotional learning (SEL), self-efficacy, and creative thinking are more strongly influenced by experiential and contextual factors than by age. This supports Cagay et al. (2024), who argue that self-efficacy alone is insufficient to predict academic performance, as motivation, learning experiences, and exposure to supportive environments play crucial roles. Hence, interventions to develop these skills should focus on experience-based learning rather than age-dependent strategies.

The significant correlations between SEL components and academic performance reinforce the findings of Khongsankham (2024), who observed that emotional regulation, empathy, and social awareness enhance students' ability to manage stress, maintain motivation, and make sound academic decisions. Schools that integrate SEL programs—through reflective journaling, peer collaboration, and conflict-resolution training—can enhance students' emotional intelligence, resulting in increased academic engagement (Schonert-Reichl, 2017).

The positive correlation between GAS and academic performance aligns with Liu et al. (2023), who found that students with higher self-efficacy persist through academic difficulties and employ more effective learning strategies. Educators can foster this by setting attainable goals, providing constructive feedback, and creating a supportive classroom climate that encourages students to take academic risks (Usher & Pajares, 2018; Zhen et al., 2020).

The relationship between creative thinking and academic performance further underscores the importance of creativity as a vital academic skill. Wardani (2023) and Beghetto & Karwowski (2017) both emphasize that creativity enhances problem-solving, adaptability, and critical thinking. Encouraging inquiry-based, interdisciplinary, and open-ended tasks can nurture flexibility and innovation among students (Henriksen et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the positive association between learning materials at home and both GAS and creative thinking is consistent with Mahama et al. (2019), who noted that access to educational resources enhances confidence and supports independent learning. Educational equity initiatives—such as digital learning programs, mobile libraries, and community tutoring—are crucial for bridging gaps in resource availability (OECD, 2016; UNESCO, 2020).

Given that these competencies are not significantly related to age, schools should prioritize experiential and socially grounded learning approaches rather than age-specific models (Elias & Haynes, 2019; Domitrovich et al., 2017). Longitudinal research is recommended to explore mediating factors influencing the interplay between SEL, GAS, creative thinking, and academic success (Jones et al., 2019).

In sum, the correlations reveal that SEL, self-efficacy, and creativity collectively enhance academic outcomes, while access to learning resources amplifies these effects. Educational policies that integrate social-emotional development, confidence building, and creative engagement—alongside equitable access to learning materials—can foster more holistic and resilient learners.

The findings indicate that socio-emotional learning (SEL), academic self-efficacy (GAS), and creative thinking (CT) are largely gender-neutral constructs. Both male and female students demonstrated comparable levels of self-awareness, emotional regulation, collaboration, and creative application, suggesting that these competencies are developed through exposure and experience, rather than being innate to gender differences. This supports the work of Adina & Colomeischi (2015) and Khongsankham (2024), who emphasized that social-emotional and creative abilities are cultivated through nurturing environments, inclusive learning opportunities, and consistent interpersonal engagement, independent of gender.

This gender neutrality highlights the effectiveness of equitable and participatory learning environments. When educators provide balanced opportunities for collaboration, self-expression, and reflection, both male and female students can develop key competencies equally. Thus, gender-inclusive pedagogies—those that ensure access, respect, and equal participation—play a central role in fostering socio-emotional and creative growth among all learners.

The significant difference in responsible decision-making, where female students scored higher, warrants particular attention. This may reflect gendered socialization patterns, in which cultural expectations encourage girls to be more

empathetic, reflective, and cautious in making decisions, whereas boys may be socialized toward assertiveness or risk-taking behaviors that do not always emphasize emotional awareness or ethical deliberation.

Educationally, this finding highlights the need for intentional interventions to support male students in developing decision-making and ethical reasoning skills. Activities such as case studies, structured debates, and guided peer dialogues can provide spaces for students to practice perspective-taking and reflective judgment. Moreover, leadership programs and service-learning projects can be powerful tools to help all students, especially males, develop responsible decision-making skills through real-world applications.

From a broader pedagogical perspective, these results contribute to the discourse on gender-sensitive education. While maintaining equality in access and expectations, educators should also recognize nuanced gender differences to deliver differentiated yet equitable instruction. As suggested by UNESCO (2020), gender-responsive pedagogy empowers teachers to adapt classroom practices to address subtle disparities and ensure that both male and female students achieve emotional, cognitive, and ethical competence.

From a policy standpoint, these findings underscore the need for inclusive SEL frameworks that are both equitable and responsive. Curriculum developers and school administrators should ensure that socio-emotional and creative learning components reflect diverse student experiences, while teacher training programs incorporate gender-awareness modules to foster inclusive classroom dynamics.

In conclusion, the Chi-Square analysis confirms that SEL, GAS, and CT are not inherently gendered skills, and they can be developed equally across both sexes. Nevertheless, the observed difference in responsible decision-making suggests that targeted efforts to strengthen ethical and reflective reasoning—especially among male students—can promote holistic development. Addressing such differences early ensures the cultivation of emotionally intelligent, socially responsible, and ethically grounded learners who are prepared for both academic and real-world challenges.

The SEM analysis provides strong empirical support for a mediated model in which Creative Thinking (CT) indirectly affects academic performance through Socio-Emotional Learning (SEL) and General Academic Self-Efficacy (GAS). The significant paths from CT to SEL and from CT to GAS align with previous research, which emphasizes that creative thinking enhances emotional regulation, adaptability, and problem-solving skills—all of which contribute to socio-emotional and self-efficacy development (Runco & Jaeger, 2012; Wardani, 2023).

The non-significant direct path from CT to Average Grade ($\beta = -0.07$, $p = .194$) suggests that creativity alone does not immediately translate into higher academic performance. This may be due to moderating factors such as teaching methods, socio-economic background, or classroom climate, which can influence how creativity manifests in academic achievement (Beghetto & Karwowski, 2017). It highlights the importance of contextual and instructional support in translating creative capacities into measurable academic outcomes.

The strong positive effects of SEL ($\beta = 3.295$) and GAS ($\beta = 6.306$) on Average Grade reinforce established evidence that emotional regulation, social competence, and self-belief significantly enhance student performance. These results are consistent with Liu et al. (2023) and Khongsankham (2024), who found that self-efficacy and socio-emotional competencies facilitate persistence, focus, and motivation in learning.

The finding that SEL and GAS fully mediate the relationship between CT and performance highlights the interconnected nature of cognitive, emotional, and motivational processes in learning. This supports a holistic educational model where creativity serves as a foundation for developing emotional intelligence and self-regulation, which in turn drive academic success. As Elias & Haynes (2019) argued, integrating social-emotional development into academic instruction fosters resilient and adaptive learners who can transfer creative problem-solving skills into real-world academic contexts.

Practically, these findings suggest that educators should design integrated learning programs that connect creative thinking exercises with SEL and self-efficacy-building activities. Examples include project-based learning, collaborative problem-solving, and reflective goal-setting, which simultaneously engage students' creativity, emotional awareness, and confidence.

From a theoretical perspective, the results contribute to the understanding that creative thinking serves as a catalyst for the development of self-belief and emotional competence, which together predict academic achievement. Future research should investigate other potential mediators, such as motivation, instructional quality, and peer support, to further refine the model and understand how creativity contributes to academic outcomes across diverse educational contexts.

In summary, the SEM results confirm that creative thinking indirectly supports academic success by influencing socio-emotional learning and self-efficacy. By integrating cognitive, emotional, and motivational dimensions, educators can cultivate students who are not only academically capable but also emotionally intelligent, self-assured, and adaptable to complex learning environments.

Moreover, the findings from Table 10 emphasize that Creative Thinking (CT) contributes to academic success indirectly by fostering Socio-Emotional Learning (SEL) and General Academic Self-Efficacy (GAS). The significant indirect effect ($\beta = 0.842$, $p < .001$) highlights that creativity influences students' academic performance through intermediary psychological and emotional pathways rather than direct cognitive mechanisms.

This mediation pathway reinforces the earlier results from the SEM analysis, demonstrating that creativity serves as a catalyst for the development of emotional intelligence and self-belief, both of which are crucial for academic resilience and performance. As Liu et al. (2023) noted, students with higher self-efficacy persist longer in academic tasks and demonstrate greater adaptability in challenging learning environments. Similarly, Khongsankham (2024) found that strong socio-emotional skills improve emotional regulation and peer collaboration, directly supporting better academic outcomes.

The magnitude of this indirect effect (0.842) suggests that even moderate improvements in creative thinking can have substantial downstream effects on performance, provided they are accompanied by interventions that strengthen SEL and self-efficacy. This aligns with Elias & Haynes (2019), who advocate for holistic educational frameworks that integrate cognitive, emotional, and motivational domains to foster optimal learning outcomes.

From a pedagogical standpoint, these results underscore the importance of designing educational programs that link creativity, emotional development, and confidence-building. Instructional strategies such as creative problem-solving workshops, collaborative design projects, and reflective learning sessions can cultivate creativity while simultaneously enhancing SEL and self-efficacy. Such integrative approaches ensure that cognitive and affective domains reinforce one another, leading to sustainable academic growth.

In conclusion, the indirect effect analysis validates the mediating role of SEL and GAS in translating creative potential into academic achievement. By embedding creativity-enhancing practices within socio-emotional and self-efficacy frameworks, educators can promote not only improved mathematics performance but also the development of well-rounded, resilient, and confident learners.

Conclusion

This study finds that creative thinking alone does not directly boost mathematics performance; instead, its positive impact depends on the presence of socio-emotional learning (SEL) and general academic self-efficacy (GAS). SEL and GAS act as essential mediators by helping students manage emotions, build confidence, and maintain motivation during math tasks. When students possess strong socio-emotional skills and high self-efficacy, they are more likely to utilize creativity effectively in mathematics, leading to improved outcomes.

The results underscore the importance of a holistic mathematics education approach that integrates cognitive skills with emotional and motivational support. Creativity's benefits are maximized only when paired with emotional intelligence and self-confidence. Addressing these interconnected factors can help educators and policymakers develop more inclusive, effective ways to enhance math learning and prepare students for academic and real-world challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed. For educators, teachers should actively integrate creative thinking activities and socio-emotional learning (SEL) strategies in mathematics instruction. Activities that encourage students to express original ideas and manage their emotions may enhance motivation and academic performance. For school administrators and institutions, programs that promote student self-efficacy—such as mentoring, collaborative learning, and reflective exercises—should be implemented to build learners' confidence in mathematics. Supportive environments can help address performance gaps among students with low self-efficacy. For curriculum developers, instructional materials should be designed to stimulate creativity and emotional engagement, especially in challenging subjects such as mathematics. This includes tasks that allow for multiple solution paths and promote self-directed learning. For future researchers, additional studies may explore the mediating role of self-efficacy in other subject areas and educational levels. It is also recommended to examine longitudinal effects and interventions that develop creative thinking and SEL over time.

Author Contributions

Both authors contributed equally to all aspects of the research. They collaborated on the conceptualization of the study, data gathering, analysis, and manuscript writing. Together, they finalized the study and jointly prepared for the research defense. Both authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

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